

Data Management plan for: Innovative Multifunctional Laser-Textured Surfaces with Improved Tribological Performance and Icephobicity (Izp-2023/1-0060)

Version 1

Description

Considering the global energy crisis and the set goals of zero emissions, it is extremely important in the regions of the Nordic countries to reduce the friction between different mechanisms and the energy losses caused by icing. There are two main methods to reduce the energy consumption caused by friction and icing, the first is the use of chemical lubricants, which can pollute the environment, and the second is the mechanical improvement of the surface properties. Laser-induced surface texturing is an effective and environmentally friendly method for improving the surface properties of materials. Two RTU institutes have formed an interdisciplinary team of researchers to develop a sustainable laser texturing method for improving the tribological and anti-icing properties of stainless steel surfaces for applications at low air temperatures. The main innovative aspect of this project lies in a new approach that uses a temperature gradient field induced by pulsed laser radiation to change the chemical composition and micro/nano-texture of the surface layer, thereby affecting the anti-icing and tribological properties of the surface. The second goal of the project is to increase the quality of fundamental knowledge in the research of tribology on ice and anti-icing processes by introducing an improved method for thermal observations of these processes and 3D measurements of the texture of modified surfaces. The surface textures obtained by the new method are mainly intended for applications at low air temperatures, but their applicability is much wider.

Funder

Innovative Multifunctional Laser-Textured Surfaces with Improved Tribological Performance and Icephobicity (Izp-2023/1-0060)

Grant

Latvian Council of Science (Innovative Multifunctional Laser-Textured Surfaces with Improved Tribological Performance and Icephobicity (Izp-2023/1-0060))

Researchers

Raimonds Sirants (orcid:0009-0003-8502-5150), Ernests Jansons (orcid:0000-0001-6526-4224), Armands Leitans (orcid:0009-0001-5690-0038), Pavels Onufrijevs (0000-0002-0554-7545), Janis Lungevics (orcid:0000-0001-6350-8838)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management plan for: Innovative Multifunctional Laser-Textured Surfaces with Improved Tribological Performance and Icephobicity \(Izp-2023/1-0060\)](#)

Description:

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Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Innovative Multifunctional Laser-Textured Surfaces with Improved Tribological Performance and Icephobicity (Izp-2023/1-0060)

Grants: Latvian Council of Science (Innovative Multifunctional Laser-Textured Surfaces with Improved Tribological Performance and Icephobicity (Izp-2023/1-0060))

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Surface texture measurements

Data from sample surface texture measurements.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data of the surface texture measurements of the samples were collected, which is important for characterizing the relationship between the surface texture and the friction properties on the ice, as well as for improving the theoretical models of the ice friction.

Data collected are direct measurements using both 2D and 3D surface texture measurement equipment.

The dataset does not include data for reuse.

The data are useful for researchers working in the field of surface measurement as well as for researchers studying processes related to ice friction.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Measurement numerical data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

MNT, UDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, because each sample is developed within the project and its surface is unique. It is not possible to use data from other samples.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The utility of this data spans across several fields where precision, quality control, and performance are critical.

Manufacturing and Quality Control

Material Science and Research

Product Development and Design

Tribology and Mechanical Systems

Optical and Surface Coating Industries

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Surface texture, 3D surface, roughness

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The specific data may be used freely, but during the project, in order to avoid misuse of the data, access to them will only be allowed by contacting the authors.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The embargo period will be at least 1 year after the project ends.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

Zenodo is an open-access data repository, adheres to the FAIR principles, provides long-term digital preservation, assigns DOI.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Software tools which can open MNT files.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

This license is widely used in the scientific and research community and ensures that the data can be reused with minimal restrictions, maximizing its impact and utility.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2028-01-03

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ernests Jansons (orcid: [0000-0001-6526-4224](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6526-4224))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Tribological experimental data

Data from Tribological experiments from dry friction tests and ice friction tests.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The tribology data obtained for both dry friction and ice friction are essential for characterizing the relationships between laser-textured surfaces and friction properties, thereby evaluating the impact of specific laser treatments. Additionally, this data will be used to improve theoretical models of ice friction.

The dataset does not include data for reuse.

The data are useful for researchers working in the field of tribology as well as for researchers studying processes related to ice friction.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Measurement numerical data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, because each sample is developed within the project and its tribological properties are unique. It is not possible to use data from other samples.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The utility of this data spans several fields where friction plays an essential role.

Manufacturing and Quality Control

Material Science and Research

Product Development and Design

Tribology and Mechanical Systems

Optical and Surface Coating Industries

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

friction, ice friction, tribology, wear

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The specific data may be used freely, but during the project, in order to avoid misuse of the data, access to them will only be allowed by contacting the authors.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The embargo period will be at least 1 year after the project ends.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

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2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Office Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

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2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2028-01-03

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3 Resources and Security

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Yes

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Yes

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No

Characterisation: (Wettability properties, Raman Spectra, XRD, SEM and Optical images etc.)

Data from surface characterisation: contact angle measurements, SEM, Optical images and Raman Spectra, XRD etc.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To characterize various surfaces, including the laser-textured surfaces planned in the project, optical microscope measurements, SEM measurements, contact angle measurements, and Raman spectra will be used. These measurements are essential both for surface characterization and for describing their properties.

Data collected are direct measurements.

The dataset does not include data for reuse.

The data are useful for researchers working in the field of surface characterization, as well as for researchers studying processes related to ice friction.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Measurement numerical data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PNG
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, because each sample is developed within the project and its surface is unique. It is not possible to use data from other samples.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The utility of this data spans across several fields where friction, wettability or de-icing properties might be important.

Manufacturing and Quality Control

Material Science and Research

Product Development and Design

Tribology and Mechanical Systems

Optical and Surface Coating Industries

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

contact angle, Raman Spectra, SEM

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

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Software tools which can open MNT files.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

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2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2028-01-03

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

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Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Microhardness measurements

Data from Microhardness measurements.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Microhardness measurements are used to characterize the impact of laser processing on changes in surface hardness.

The dataset does not include data for reuse.

The data are useful for researchers working in the field of tribology as well as for researchers studying processes related to ice friction.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Measurement numerical data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, because each sample is developed within the project and its tribological properties are unique. It is not possible to use data from other samples.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The utility of this data spans several fields where microhardness plays an essential role.

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Material Science and Research

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2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

microhardness

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

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